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ABSTRACT

We prepared a Mn₄₈Fe₂₂P₁₅Si₁₅ glass-coated microwires (GCMWS) with metallic nucleus diameter, $d = 11.2 \mu\text{m}$ and total diameter, $D = 28.3 \mu\text{m}$ (geometrical aspect ratio $d/D = 0.4$) for the first time by using the Taylor–Ulitsky Technique. This low-cost, single-step fabrication approach enabled the preparation of kilometers-long GCMWS from a few grams of low-cost components (Mn, Fe, P, and Si) for a variety of applications. The analysis of the magnetic measurements revealed a well-defined magnetic anisotropy in the whole temperature range. Moreover, relatively hard magnetic properties were observed for the temperature range of 5–400 K, where the average of coercivity, $H_c \approx 465 \text{ Oe}$. Notable magnetic field, H , and temperature dependencies of the magnetic properties were observed. Substantially irreversible magnetic behavior with a blocking temperatures $T_b = 97 \text{ K}$ at $H = 1 \text{ kOe}$ and $T_b = 50 \text{ K}$ at $H = 5 \text{ kOe}$ upon field cooling was observed. The modification in the magnetic properties of MnFePSi-glass-coated microwires is ascribed to the presence of various magnetic phases resulting from internal stresses induced by the glass coating. Moreover, the elevated Curie temperature ($T_c > 400 \text{ K}$) observed in the investigated sample, makes this material as an appealing choice for several industrial applications.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Glass-coated microwires (GCMWs) are among the most promising materials for sensor technology.^{1,2} Such microwires, often just a few micrometres in diameter, consist of a metallic nucleus coated with thin insulating glass coating.^{1–4} This distinct structure confers several advantages to glass-coated microwires, prompting extensive research and application in various industrial sectors.^{5,6} Typically, the metallic nucleus is prepared from ferromagnetic elements, such as Fe, Ni, Mn or Co and their alloys.^{5–16} The choice of metallic nucleus chemical composition is determined by the applications of microwires. Thus, Fe-based microwires, are often employed

in magnetoelastic sensors, whereas Co-based microwires are often proposed for magnetic field sensors.

The glass coating, on the other hand, serves several purposes. It protects the metallic nucleus mechanically, maintaining its integrity even when using brittle metallic nucleus alloys (i.e. nanocrystalline materials or Heusler type alloy). In addition, the insulating glass coating prevents electrical short circuits, improves corrosion resistance and provides biocompatibility.^{6,8,12,16} In addition, the glass shell acts as an insulator, preventing electrical short circuits, increasing corrosion resistance and providing biocompatibility. During the GCMWs manufacture, the thickness of the glass coating layer can be carefully adjusted, allowing it to be tailored to particular

sensing requirements.⁶ The Taylor-Ulitovsky fabrication process for GCMWs preparation briefly consists of drawing a thin metallic microwire inside a glass capillary, which forms the glass coating around the metallic nucleus. This method is suitable for fabrication of GCMWs with metallic nucleus diameters $0.1 \leq d \leq 100 \mu\text{m}$ and described in details elsewhere.⁶ However, preparation of such composite GCMWs, involving rapid solidification of metallic nucleus inside the glass-coating, is associated with elevated internal stresses.^{1,11,13}

MnFePSi alloys, which are one of the rapidly expanding families of magnetocaloric materials, has attracted substantial attention in recent years owing to their exceptional magnetic and structural properties.^{17,18} This alloy is characterized by its unique electronic structure, which imparts unique attributes such as high magnetocaloric effect (MCE) and saturation magnetization.¹⁷⁻¹⁹ Furthermore, $(\text{Mn,Fe})_2(\text{P,Si})$ materials are among the most promising alloys because they provide ideal conditions for practical applications (low-cost starting materials and environmental advantages).¹⁸ For emerging technological applications, the miniaturization of the devices based on fine MCE particles, wires, ribbons, films, bi- and multilayers, and pillars is crucial.¹⁸⁻²⁶ Thus, from the perspective of the use of MCE, the manufacture of thin wires from brittle MnFePSi alloy could be interesting.

In this work, we provide results on a primary investigation of the morphological and magnetic properties of MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwires.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

The following raw materials were used to create an ingot: Mn (99.5%), pieces of FeP (98%) P (99.5%) and Si (99.999%). The ingot was fabricated using arc-melting in an argon environment to avoid the oxidations of the alloy. An extra 5 weight percent of manganese

was added to FeP, P and Si to make up for the Mn that was lost during the arc-melting process. The ingot was electromagnetically stirred at least six times before being suction cast into an 8 mm diameter rod for melt extraction into microwires. Energy-dispersive X-ray (EDX) analysis was then used to confirm the nominal composition, revealing the actual composition to be $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$. Once we had the alloy, we used the Taylor-Ulitovsky method to manufacture the MnFePSi-GCMWs.^{6,8,10} Creating the glass capillary, pulling the composite microwire—a metal nucleus wrapped in glass—straight from the molten master alloy, and melting the previously produced alloy within the glass tube using a high-frequency inductor are all steps in this production process. After the molten metallic alloy fills the glass capillary during the drawing step, a glass-coated microwire is produced.⁶⁻¹² Lastly, the metallic core of the microwire is entirely encased in a continuous, flexible, and insulating glass covering.

This preparation process includes producing the glass capillary, melting the previously prepared alloy inside the glass tube with a high-frequency inductor, and pulling the composite microwire (metal nucleus covered by glass) directly from the molten master alloy.^{6,12} Finally, we obtained a metallic nucleus covered by an insulating, flexible, and continuous glass-coating.

A vibrating sample magnetometer (PPMS, Physical Property Magnetic System, Quantum Design Inc., San Diego, CA, USA) was used to measure the magnetization curves at temperatures (T) ranging from 5 to 400 K and magnetic fields up to 9T.

III. RESULTS

Figure 1 illustrates the morphological and chemical composition of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ obtained by SEM/EDX. As seen in Fig. 1 the elements of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ have a homogeneous distribution.

FIG. 1. (a) SEM image of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires and (b) the chemical composition spectra of EDX at one of the points. (c) The atomic mass of Mn, Fe, P and Si elemental composition in $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires.

Figure 2 shows the in-plane hysteresis loops of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ -GCMWs. As seen in Fig. 2, rectangular M - H loops are observed at a wide range of measuring temperatures from 300 K to 150 K. In addition, the coercivity shows a slight increase from 450 Oe at $T = 300$ K to 465 Oe at $T = 150$ K. Enhanced coercivity, H_c , values for $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires are observed for the first time. It looks unusual, compared to other MnFePSi samples, such as ribbons, bulk and thin films, where such alloys usually present quite soft magnetic behavior.^{17,19–23} The magnetic properties of MnFePSi alloys are strongly affected by the chemical composition and microstructure.^{18–26} The unusually elevated H_c -values observed in MnFePSi-based glass-coated microwires can be related either to the elevated internal stresses associated with the glass-coating layer, induced during the fabrication process or different microstructure compared to other MnFePSi-samples. The glass-coating not only originates the strong internal stresses but also affects the quenching rate due to the low thermal conductivity of glass.⁶

Examining the MnFePSi-GCMWs whole magnetic behaviour at various temperatures is essential for assessing its thermal stability, a crucial characteristic that will help determine its potential suitability for spintronics applications. Magnetic phase transitions may

also be accessed through the temperature dependence of magnetic properties. We have investigated the magnetization dependence on temperature (M vs. T), i.e., field cooling (FC), and field heating (FH), for as-prepared MnFePSi-GCMWs using a magnetic field ($H = 1$ k and 5 k Oe) and a temperature, T , range from 5 to 400 K (see Fig. 3). The FC and FH curves show that the Curie temperature, T_c , of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ -GCMWs is above 400 K. In fact, this is a substantial difference between the studied $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ -GCMWs and the other samples of the same composition, in which T_c is below room temperature. As can be seen in Figure 3a, the FH curve presents a ferromagnetic behavior, in which the magnetizations increase monotonically as the temperature decreases from 400 to 5 K. Meanwhile, a difference in FH and FC curves and a blocking temperature, T_b , are observed at $T = 97$ K in the FC curve. This blocking temperature is shifted to a lower temperature by increasing the external magnetic field from 1 kOe to 5 kOe, where T_b is reduced from 97 K to 50 K (see Figure 3b). This blocking temperature is shifted to a lower temperature by increasing the external magnetic field from 1 kOe to 5 kOe: T_b decreased from 97 K to 50 K (see Figure 3b). The magnetic field dependence of the FC and FH curves illustrates the magnetic field and temperature sensitivity

FIG. 2. (a-d) M - H loops, measured in magnetic field applied parallel to the axis of microwires in the temperature range from 150 to 300 K for as-prepared $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ -GCMWs.

FIG. 3. Magnetization vs temperature curves in two main configuration field cooling (FC) and field heating (FH) of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ -GCMWs for T range from 5-400 K and applied magnetic field (a) $H = 1$ kOe and (b) 5 kOe.

of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ -GCMWs and can be attributed to the complex microstructure of the studied samples.

As discussed above, the difference in the magnetic properties of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires compared to previously studied MnFePSi materials may be due to elevated internal stresses values, as well as the influence of insulating glass-coating on quenching rate (originated by low thermal conductivity of glass) during the microwires preparation.⁶

Future structural studies may help to understand the unusual magnetic behavior of $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, we succeeded in fabricating $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires with total diameter of 28.3 μm and diameter of a metallic nucleus diameter of about 11.2 μm . The morphological and chemical properties analysis performed by SEM/EDX confirms the homogeneity of formation of uniform $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires. The magnetic analysis reveals enhanced coercivity values of about 465 Oe at $T = 150$ K. The thermal magnetic behavior of MnFePSi glass-coated microwires shows interesting magnetic behavior, where the blocking temperature observed at field cooling shifts to $T = 50$ K by increasing applied external magnetic field from 1 kOe to 5 kOe. To clarify the effects of annealing

conditions and geometrical factors on magneto-structural and thermoelectric characteristics, further investigation is needed. Obtained results open the possibility of using $\text{Mn}_{48}\text{Fe}_{22}\text{P}_{15}\text{Si}_{15}$ glass-coated microwires with unusual magnetization behavior, especially when it comes to changing the magnetic and micromagnetic phase and structure to create thermomagnetic switching spintronic devices.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Mohamed Salaheldeen: Conceptualization (equal); Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Validation (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – original draft (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Valentina Zhukova:** Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Project administration (equal); Supervision (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **J. J. Rosero-Romo:** Data curation (equal). **Mihail Ipatov:** Data curation (equal). **Arcady Zhukov:** Conceptualization (equal); Funding acquisition (equal); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Visualization (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding authors upon reasonable request.

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